

Effect of Solvents on the Spectra of Carboxyalkyl and Thiazolyl Substituted Thiocarbamides

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Electronic absorption spectra of twenty one carboxyalkyl and thiazolyl substituted thiocarbamides have been examined in a series of solvents covering a broad polarity range i.e. from chloroform (Z 63.2) to methanol (Z 83.6). Transition energies were calculated and plotted against Z -values, a new empirical measurement of solvent polarity. A linear relationship was observed between transition energy (E_T) and Z . Solvent sensitivities of these ligands have been calculated.

CARBOXYALKYL and thiazolyl substituted thiocarbamides constitute an important class of compounds because of their increasing utilisation in everyday life. Some work has been reported on their preparation, ionisation constants and antifungal activity etc¹⁻⁴. Survey of the literature reveals that a little work has been reported on the spectral studies of these thiocarbamides. The purpose of present study is to find out the effect of solvents of different polarity on the electronic transitions of carboxyalkyl and thiazolyl thiocarbamides. An attempt has been made to analyse the results in terms of solvent polarity parameter.

Experimental

The compounds selected for the present study were *N*-methyl-*N'*-(2-phenyl-1-carboxyethyl)thiocarbamide (METuH), *N*-phenyl-*N'*-(2-phenyl-1-carboxyethyl)thiocarbamide (PETuH), *N*-allyl-*N'*-(2-phenyl-1-carboxyethyl)thiocarbamide (AETuH), *N*-methyl-*N'*-[1-carboxy-5-(*N''*-methylthiocarbamido)pentyl]thiocarbamide (MPTuH), *N*-phenyl-*N'*-[1-carboxy-5-(*N''*-phenylthiocarbamido)pentyl]thiocarbamide (PPTuH), *N*-allyl-*N'*-[1-carboxy-5-(*N''*-allylthiocarbamido)pentyl]thiocarbamide (APTuH), *N*-methyl-*N'*-[4-carboxy-4-(*N''*-methylthiocarbamido)butylamido]thiocarbamide (MBATuH), *N*-phenyl-*N'*-[4-carboxy-4-(*N''*-phenylthiocarbamido)butylamido]thiocarbamide (PBATuH), *N*-allyl-*N'*-[4-carboxy-4-(*N''*-allylthiocarbamido)butylamido]thiocarbamide (ABATuH), *N*-methyl-*N'*-[4-carboxy-4-(*N''*-methylthiocarbamido)butanoyl]thiocarbamide (MBTuH), *N*-phenyl-*N'*-[4-carboxy-4-(*N''*-phenylthiocarbamido)butanoyl]thiocarbamide (PBTuH), *N*-allyl-*N'*-[4-car-

boxy-4-*N''*-(allylthiocarbamido)butanoyl]thiocarbamide (ABTuH), *N*-methyl-*N'*-(carboxymethyl)thiocarbamide (MCMTuH), *N*-phenyl-*N'*-(carboxymethyl)thiocarbamide (PCMTuH), *N*-allyl-*N'*-(carboxymethyl)thiocarbamide (ACMTuH), *N*-methyl-*N'*-2-(4-phenylthiazolyl)thiocarbamide (MPTTuH), *N*-phenyl-*N'*-2-(4-phenylthiazolyl)thiocarbamide (PPTTuH), *N*-allyl-*N'*-2-(4-phenylthiazolyl)thiocarbamide (APTtuH), *N*-methyl-*N'*-2-(4-methylthiazolyl)thiocarbamide (MMTTuH), *N*-phenyl-*N'*-2-(4-methylthiazolyl)thiocarbamide (PMTTuH), and *N*-allyl-*N'*-2-(4-methylthiazolyl)thiocarbamide (AMTTuH). The compounds were synthesised as described earlier^{5,6}. All the solvents used were of either AnalaR or E. Merck G. R. grade. Freshly distilled solvents⁷ were used in all the experiments and the solutions were prepared immediately before use. The absorbance measurements were made at $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$ with a PMQ-3 UV-VIS spectrophotometer using 1 cm matched quartz cells equipped with thermoplates to stabilise the temperature. The results are reported in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

It is evident from the results reported in Table 1 that all the substituted-carboxyalkylthiocarbamides exhibit three intense absorption maxima in the range of 206–214, 230–250 and 261–275 nm, assigned to high energy $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ carboxyalkyl transition, thiocarbonyl $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition and $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ carboxyaryl transition^{8,9}, respectively. The thiazolylthiocarbamides (Table 1) also show three intense bands at 207–212, 231–250, 280–288 nm, assigned

TABLE I—SPECTRAL DATA OF THE SUBSTITUTED-THIOCARBAMIDES IN DIFFERENT SOLVENTS

Compd.	Methanol (MeOH)		Ethanol (EtOH)		Acetonitrile (AN)		Dimethyl sulphoxide (DMSO)		Chloroform (CF)	
	$\lambda_{\max}$	$\epsilon_{\max}$	$\lambda_{\max}$	$\epsilon_{\max}$	$\lambda_{\max}$	$\epsilon_{\max}$	$\lambda_{\max}$	$\epsilon_{\max}$	$\lambda_{\max}$	$\epsilon_{\max}$
Carboxyalkyl-substituted-thiocarbamides										
METuH	207	21 375	208	21 575	210	21 780	209	19 670	209	21 960
	240	13 200	239	13 560	244	14 010	249	11 540	244	13 880
	270	17 673	272	18 110	267	13 540	273	17 320	273	18 475
PETuH	209	22 656	210	22 910	208	23 110	211	20 570	211	23 720
	233	12 990	237	13 320	243	13 910	246	10 860	243	13 590
	269	18 334	271	18 870	266	19 100	272	17 640	273	19 920
AETuH	203	20 180	209	20 570	207	20 810	210	19 720	210	20 980
	240	11 950	239	12 320	245	12 800	248	10 640	244	12 650
	268	18 954	269	19 110	270	19 540	272	17 680	272	19 756
MPTuH	203	16 990	207	17 210	211	17 420	210	15 310	212	17 640
	241	22 524	240	22 810	246	23 420	249	20 310	245	23 205
	269	17 180	267	17 770	272	18 210	274	15 810	272	17 985
PPTuH	207	17 580	206	17 870	210	17 910	208	15 870	209	18 160
	241	21 626	240	22 010	246	22 400	249	19 810	246	22 220
	268	16 585	266	16 840	271	17 110	272	15 640	272	17 280
APTuH	208	16 489	207	16 780	210	17 110	211	15 840	210	17 110
	240	22 626	239	22 910	246	23 420	250	20 410	245	23 120
	266	17 635	267	17 910	270	18 340	268	16 690	270	18 435
MBATuH	211	22 520	210	22 820	208	23 110	209	20 410	213	23 120
	235	24 710	234	25 110	240	25 540	245	22 160	240	25 830
	272	30 700	270	31 140	268	31 480	273	28 670	275	31 120
PBATuH	209	24 526	213	24 820	212	25 010	210	21 840	211	25 120
	238	25 110	237	25 440	243	25 920	246	23 010	244	25 760
	270	31 415	272	31 820	270	32 110	274	29 760	274	31 815
ABATuH	210	23 330	209	23 680	211	24 110	211	22 320	212	23 930
	236	25 320	235	25 610	242	26 010	245	22 320	241	26 210
	270	32 210	267	32 810	271	33 140	275	31 080	272	32 920
MBTuH	208	7 715	207	7 920	210	8 010	212	7 080	211	8 320
	230	12 605	230	13 010	236	13 480	241	10 510	235	13 310
	263	16 510	264	17 110	267	17 640	270	15 320	267	17 120
PBTuH	206	7 810	207	8 210	209	8 540	211	7 010	209	8 515
	233	12 810	232	13 310	239	13 940	243	10 640	238	13 520
	266	16 875	264	17 640	268	18 110	270	15 650	270	17 740
ABTuH	207	7 605	208	7 885	209	8 010	210	7 304	210	8 320
	235	12 910	234	13 240	240	13 830	245	10 810	239	13 620
	268	17 720	265	18 230	270	18 640	271	16 640	271	18 380
MOMTuH	209	12 620	208	13 110	210	13 420	211	10 570	211	13 210
	231	15 510	230	16 010	236	16 620	242	13 840	237	16 230
	262	23 200	261	23 640	266	24 110	268	20 880	265	23 820
POMTuH	208	13 105	206	13 710	210	13 840	212	11 720	211	13 710
	233	16 105	232	16 610	238	17 320	244	14 010	238	16 875
	265	23 810	263	24 320	267	24 710	269	21 410	268	23 400
ACOMTuH	210	13 810	209	14 220	211	14 530	211	11 480	212	14 450
	234	16 760	233	17 110	240	17 610	245	14 640	239	17 580
	268	24 010	264	24 604	268	24 675	270	21 380	271	24 670
Thiazolyl-substituted thiocarbamides										
MPTTuH	210	20 818	209	21 110	210	21 780	212	19 940	212	21 520
	232	31 665	231	31 845	238	32 110	245	29 780	236	32 340
	280	14 412	231	14 910	234	15 140	235	13 950	234	15 115
PPTTuH	208	20 516	208	21 110	211	21 450	211	19 420	211	21 210
	234	33 415	233	33 720	240	34 110	246	31 100	239	34 410
	282	14 925	282	15 320	285	15 710	284	14 120	285	15 530
APTTuH	207	21 425	210	21 710	212	22 210	210	20 010	210	21 930
	233	32 312	232	32 720	239	33 100	244	30 310	238	33 110
	283	13 200	283	13 540	283	13 830	286	11 790	286	13 820
MMTTuH	208	13 620	207	14 220	210	14 670	212	12 980	211	14 220
	238	17 820	237	18 140	245	18 760	250	16 140	242	18 630
	282	21 620	283	22 310	285	22 840	288	20 667	285	22 210
PMTTuH	210	14 870	209	15 360	211	15 640	211	13 780	212	15 460
	236	18 830	235	19 170	242	19 420	249	16 630	240	19 610
	281	22 410	282	22 910	286	23 120	287	20 450	284	23 970
AMTTuH	207	14 120	208	14 740	209	15 120	212	13 320	210	14 810
	238	18 180	237	18 570	245	18 960	250	16 510	244	18 970
	285	22 110	284	22 840	284	23 110	288	21 210	288	23 830

* $\lambda_{\max}$, nm, ϵ , $\text{dm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$.

to thiazolyl $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$, thiocarbonyl $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ and high energy transition of 2-substituted-thiazolyl group, respectively¹⁰. These bands exhibit a small shift in different solvents of varying polarities and is in consistent with the expected spectra of a molecule having an excited state which is more polar than the ground state.

The $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions of carboxyalkyl group fall in the range 206–214 nm. This band appears to be mixed with some other transitions probably $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions of carboxyl group overlapping with it. In case of thiazolylthiocarbamides, high energy $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions are observed in the region 207–212 nm. These transitions have moderate intensity and moderate oscillator strength. Plots of Z vs E_T were drawn and straight line was obtained by least-square fit. Deviations in case of acetonitrile (AN) and dimethyl sulphoxide (DMSO) can be explained by considering the charge transfer interactions between carboxyalkyl group or thiazolyl group and the solvent sensitivities obtained as the difference between the transition energies of these compounds in methanol and chloroform; and that obtained from the regression line are given in Table 2. E_T obtained by multiplying the slope by Z values difference between the solvent (ΔZ) is lower in METuH, PETuH, AETuH, PPTuH, APTuH, MBATuH, PBATuH, ABATuH, MBTuH, PBTuH, ABTuH, MCMTuH, PCMTuH, ACMTuH, MPTTuH, APTTuH and AMTTuH, and in other thiocarbamides it is higher. The slope m is related to the transition energy by the equation,

$$m = dE_T/dZ$$

Thiocarbonyl $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions of medium intensities and moderate oscillator strength, fall in the region from 230–250 nm in case of carboxyalkyl-thiocarbamides and 231–250 nm in case of thiazolyl-thiocarbamides. In this case blue-shifts are observed as one goes from chloroform to methanol. This band appears to be mixed with $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions and $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions of C=O in case of MBTuH, PBTuH and ABTuH and of C=NH in case of MBATuH, PBATuH and ABATuH. The plots of Z vs E_T were drawn and a straight line was obtained by least-square fit method. Deviations in case of DMSO can be explained by considering the charge transfer interactions between the thiocarbonyl group and the solvent. Deviations in case of AN may be due to the presence of polarised π -bond in the solvent molecule which enables the easy acceptance of electrons from the S of thiocarbonyl group resulting in the formation of a complex¹¹. The solvent sensitivity was measured as the difference in the excitation energies in methanol and chloroform (Table 2). The solvent sensitivities evaluated from the graph show a marked difference from the previous values. This is attributed to $Z - E_T$ correlation being only approximate in nature in case of bulky molecules. The solvent sensitivities of these transitions are higher in case of PPTuH, PBATuH, MBTuH, MPTTuH, PPTTuH, APTTuH and PMTTuH, and lower in the other thiocarbamides.

Transitions of similar solvent sensitivities, relatively high intensities and high oscillator strength are classified as $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions. The carboxyalkyl $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions occur at

TABLE 2—SOLVENT SENSITIVITY OF CARBOXYALKYL- AND THIAZOLYL-SUBSTITUTED-THIOCARBAMIDES

Compd.	High Energy $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition			$\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition			$n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition		
	E_T	$E_T = mz + b$		E_T	$E_T = mz + b$		E_T	$E_T = mz + b$	
	kJ mol^{-1}	m	mz kJ mol^{-1}	kJ mol^{-1}	m	mz kJ mol^{-1}	kJ mol^{-1}	m	mz kJ mol^{-1}
METuH	5.53	0.255	5.20	8.17	0.375	7.65	4.87	0.250	5.10
PETuH	5.43	0.250	5.10	10.34	0.500	10.20	6.52	0.255	5.20
AETuH	5.48	0.250	5.10	8.17	0.375	7.65	6.57	0.255	5.20
MPTuH	10.85	0.562	11.40	8.10	0.375	7.65	4.91	0.187	3.81
PPTuH	5.53	0.250	5.10	10.09	0.500	10.20	6.57	0.255	5.20
APTuH	5.48	0.250	5.10	10.17	0.497	8.91	6.66	0.255	5.20
MBATuH	5.33	0.250	5.10	10.60	0.500	10.20	4.80	0.250	5.10
PBATuH	5.43	0.250	5.10	12.36	0.625	12.75	6.47	0.255	5.20
ABATuH	5.37	0.250	5.10	10.52	0.497	8.91	3.26	0.187	3.81
MBTuH	8.18	0.375	7.65	11.07	0.625	12.75	6.81	0.312	6.36
PBTuH	8.33	0.375	7.65	10.78	0.500	10.20	6.66	0.312	6.36
ABTuH	8.26	0.375	7.65	8.59	0.375	7.65	4.95	0.250	5.10
MCMTuH	5.43	0.250	5.10	13.11	0.625	12.75	5.17	0.250	5.10
PCMTuH	8.18	0.375	7.65	10.78	0.500	10.20	5.05	0.250	5.10
ACMTuH	5.37	0.250	5.10	10.70	0.500	10.20	4.95	0.250	5.10
MPTTuH	5.37	0.250	5.10	8.74	0.497	8.91	6.02	0.312	6.36
PPTTuH	8.18	0.437	8.91	10.70	0.625	12.75	4.47	0.250	5.10
APTTuH	8.26	0.375	7.65	10.78	0.625	12.75	4.44	0.250	5.10
MMTTuH	8.18	0.437	8.91	8.31	0.375	7.65	4.47	0.250	5.10
PMTTuH	5.37	0.312	6.36	8.45	0.437	8.91	4.50	0.250	5.10
AMTTuH	8.26	0.375	7.65	12.36	0.562	11.40	4.37	0.250	5.10

261–275 nm, whereas in thiazolythiocarbamides, thiazolyl $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions occur at 280–288 nm. The $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions in all these compounds, show a blue-shift on going from chloroform ($Z=63.2$) to methanol ($Z=83.6$). From Table I it is observed that, in general, the absorption maxima in case of METuH, MPTuH, ABTuH, ACMTuH, APTTuH and AMTTuH occur at longer wavelengths in comparison to the other substituted-thiocarbamides. This difference in the position of $\lambda_{\max}$ is due to the fact that $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions of allyl group get superimposed with the $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions of carboxyalkyl and thiazolyl groups. The $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions are very much similar in character and there is considerable variation in the intensities of these bands. The transition energies (E_T) of these carboxyalkyl and thiazolyl substituted thiocarbamides were plotted against Z values and a straight line was obtained by least-square fit method. The deviation in case of DMSO is attributed due to the charge transfer interaction between thiazolyl group and the solvent in thiazolythiocarbamides, whereas in case of carboxyalkylthiocarbamides it may be due to the interaction between the carbonyl group and the solvent. High value of E_T in acetonitrile may be due to the presence of polarised $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ bands which enables easy acceptance of electrons from the S of enthiolate ion by forming a

complex^{1,2}. Since the molecules are bulky, it is difficult to achieve a fruitful relationship between Z and E_T . It is due to the fact that as the solute molecules increase in size, the correlation becomes less precise due to the specific solvent-solvent interactions, self-association and distortion of cybotactic region^{1,2}.

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